

Insights on Patient and Public Involvement and Engagement from the Eastern SDE VISTA project

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Insights on Patient and Public Involvement and Engagement from the Eastern SDE VISTA project

Final Report

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1. Executive summary

Rather than producing a standalone Patient and Public Involvement and Engagement (PPIE) strategy for VISTA, we intentionally embedded PPIE within the established infrastructure of the Eastern England SDE (EE-SDE)¹, ensuring continuity, consistency and alignment with existing work and best practice. This approach enabled us to adapt well-established PPIE mechanisms to the specific aims of VISTA, while maintaining strong and meaningful public involvement throughout the project lifecycle.

Our primary mechanism for public involvement was through the Core Public Advisory Group² (CPAG), a small, diverse group of public contributors from across the East of England and East Midlands. The CPAG meets regularly (approximately monthly) with the SDE team to provide public perspectives, challenge assumptions, and advise on the development and governance of the programme. VISTA was introduced to CPAG in April 2025 as an early-adopter project within the DARE UK TRevolution programme, with a clear outline of its objectives and intended delivery up to March 2026.

From the outset, VISTA was framed as a practical way to explore:

- How research involving artificial intelligence (AI) models can be safely supported within SDEs
- How semi-automation can be used to support the checking of research outputs before they leave the SDE
- How these complex technical processes can be governed, trusted, and clearly explained to the public

Two core technical workstreams underpin the VISTA project; SATRE³, supports standardisation of how Trusted Research Environments (TREs) are built and operated, and SACRO⁴/SACRO-ML⁵, (Semi-Automated Checking of Research Outputs) strengthen output checking through semi-automation and, in time, machine learning. Although technical, these strands led contributors to focus on broader issues including trust, transparency, accountability and proportional oversight. Contributors consistently stressed that technology should strengthen governance and not replace human judgement.

Public contributors were particularly interested in understanding how their involvement would be structured over time, especially given that the EE-SDE is already built to SATRE principles. Positioning the SDE as a reference implementation, or “gold standard,” for others developing TREs provided significant reassurance. CPAG members expressed strong interest in remaining closely involved in this journey, recognising the value of contributing public insight to the ongoing standardisation of secure data access at a national level.

2. Project background

VISTA (Viable Implementation of SATRE, SACRO and Tools for AI) is one of the DARE UK Early Adopter projects launched in January 2025 Led by Cambridge University Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust in partnership with Health Innovation East and Cambridge University Health Partners, VISTA is piloting TRevolution standards and AI capabilities within the EE-SDE.

The aims of VISTA were to support and enhance existing EE-SDE processes. Demonstrating how large-scale AI-enabled research can be conducted safely, efficiently and consistently, whilst helping other TREs adopt these approaches. There were four specific aims:

- Complete a structured self-assessment against the SATRE benchmark specification and develop actionable recommendations to inform the next phase of TRE development
- Test and refine the use of semi-automated research output checking within the Eastern England SDE
- Safely train and export outputs from AI and machine learning models
- Support AI model readiness for real-world deployment in NHS services, benefitting patients and the public

VISTA tested and enhanced existing tools for safer health research, demonstrating their viability in a live TRE operational setting. The toolset workstreams, SACRO and SACRO-ML, represent tangible resources for researchers looking to engage with semi-automated output checking, providing ante-hoc and post-hoc privacy assessment capabilities. The SATRE workstream aims to standardise how Trusted Research Environments are built and operated, providing a consistent framework for development and assessment.

This report focuses on lessons and insights from embedding PPIE in all VISTA project workstreams, combining both existing EE-SDE PPIE activities with opportunities to engage with PPIE TRevolution initiatives which has strengthened and deepened our approach and practice.

Specifically, this report focuses on capturing lessons learned from public involvement activities, identifying areas where engagement practices can be strengthened, demonstrating how public contributors influenced programme learning and highlighting where continuous improvement will benefit national data infrastructure programmes.

3. Feedback and lessons learned

We intentionally embedded PPIE within the established infrastructure of the Eastern England SDE and combined this with associated national activities focused on Trusted Research Environments (TREs), Secure Data Environments (SDEs), and AI governance frameworks.

This report summarises the Patient and Public Involvement and Engagement (PPIE) learnings gathered by the VISTA team across a series of national and programme-level activities. These activities included:

- Collaboration Cafés linked to national initiatives such as TREvolution, SATRE, and PANORAMA
- Core Public Advisory Group (CPAG) meetings
- Public contributor participation in the Trusted Research Environment (TRE) Conference
- Public involvement in governance discussions relating to AI, statistical disclosure control (SDC), and data governance

The aim of these activities was to ensure that public perspectives meaningfully inform the governance, design, and communication of complex data infrastructure initiatives. Engagements took place within a technically complex landscape involving Secure Data Environments (SDEs), AI governance frameworks, and research data governance mechanisms. While these areas are often highly technical, they are also closely linked to public trust, transparency, and confidence in how sensitive health and population data are accessed, safeguarded, and used.

The findings presented here are aligned with the PEDRI Good Practice Standards for Public Involvement⁶ and reference the National Institute for Health and Care Research (NIHR) UK Standards for Public Involvement⁷.

3.1. Collaboration Cafés (TREvolution, SATRE and Cross-SDE Engagement)

Collaboration Cafés were national knowledge-sharing sessions designed to bring together:

- Public contributors
- Researchers
- Governance experts
- Programme teams

The sessions discussed emerging issues relating to Trusted Research Environments (TREs) and associated governance frameworks, with the aim of promoting shared learning, supporting collaboration across programmes, and enabling public contributors to engage in discussions around topics such as data tiering and assurance frameworks.

3.1.1. Key Learning Themes - Transparency and Clarity of Purpose (PEDRI Standard: Transparency and Accountability)

The first Collaboration Café demonstrated that high-level agendas alone are insufficient when engaging public contributors in technically complex discussions.

Public contributors reported uncertainty about the overall purpose of the session, the specific objectives of the breakout sessions, and their input would ultimately be used, including the extent to which their contributions would shape decisions or influence outcomes.

One contributor reported:

"I was unable to contribute any meaningful input during the breakout session. It wasn't very clear what the objectives were." Public contributor

Another contributor disengaged early due to the format being perceived as confusing. However, another participant highlighted positive learning outcomes, noting that the session helped clarify how SATRE fits within the wider DARE UK landscape.

Public contributors shared candid reflections about their experience of the Collaboration Cafés, highlighting strengths, barriers and the learning environment created through these sessions. These insights directly link to PEDRI Standards on Support & Learning, Inclusive Communication, and Equity. They illustrate where the format worked well and where adjustments were needed to ensure contributors felt confident and included:

"It's been like an informal learning and baseline learning sets, no matter the amount I still don't know, I learn something new at each collaboration cafe. As a public member it can be daunting but in reality, it's very welcoming and all those who live it 'day in day out' as paid staff, take time to explain and accommodate questions." Public contributor

"I like the fact that the PPI members were invited to the TRevolution cafes as it felt like we were involved in the VISTA project discussions and problem solving. My main issue was following some of the language and concepts mentioned in the discussions as we are working with people who are experts in their field. It has been a positive learning experience but has identified that training in the use of AI and data would be beneficial for lay members." Public contributor

"I'm not a technical person – where can people like me really contribute?" Public contributor

"We need time to absorb things – some topics are incredibly complex, even for you!" (Said after explanations of SACRO and researcher annotation.) Public contributor

Public contributors require clear explanations, both before and after the event, outlining the sessions objectives, defining any key terminology, and clarifying how their contributions will be used.

3.1.2. Key Learning Themes - Power-Sharing and Participation (PEDRI Standard: Power-Sharing and Decision-Making)

The structure of the inaugural session unintentionally reinforced power imbalances between professional and public participants. Public contributors joined earlier than professionals without clear explanation and were quickly moved into breakout sessions with minimal facilitation. This reduced opportunities for equitable participation and left some contributors feeling marginalised. The consequences were significant, with one public contributor requesting to leave CPAG following the event.

Meaningful involvement requires the intentional design of facilitation approaches, discussion formats and mechanisms that ensure equal participation.

3.1.3. Key Learning Themes - Capacity Building in Technical Contexts (PEDRI Standard: Support and Learning)

Technical language and specialist terminology created barriers to engagement. For example, contributors suggested that the term “data classification” would have been clearer than “data tiering”.

A later Collaboration Café focusing on SATRE accreditation and sustainability was better received due to improved structure and clearer explanations. A key finding was that technical engagement requires accessible language, structured learning support and clear explanations of complex concepts.

3.1.4. Key Learning Themes - Psychological Safety and Inclusion (PEDRI Standard: Equity, Diversity and Inclusion)

Experiences varied widely among public contributors. Where contributors felt uncertain about expectations or unable to follow discussions, their confidence and willingness to participate were negatively affected. Conversely, when concerns were addressed through follow-up discussions and reassurance, engagement improved. A lesson learned was that psychological safety is essential to inclusive public involvement and programmes must therefore consider confidence levels, the emotional experience of participation and the support mechanisms required for contributors to enable their meaningful engagement.

3.1.5. Key Learning Themes - Impact and Feedback Loops (PEDRI Standard: Impact and Value)

Structured debrief discussions following the initial Collaboration Café allowed the VISTA team to capture detailed feedback. This feedback was shared with the TREvolution programme and contributed to improvements in subsequent sessions. The proactive approach taken by programme teams in seeking feedback demonstrates the value of formal feedback loops in improving public involvement practice. The lesson to be learnt here is that protected debrief spaces and structured feedback mechanisms are essential for ensuring that public input leads to tangible improvements.

3.2. Introduction to VISTA CPAG Meeting

The VISTA CPAG meeting brought public contributors together with programme leads to explore key elements of emerging governance within the Secure Data Environment, including AI risk assessment, SACRO-ML, statistical disclosure control and the practical safeguards that underpin responsible data access. The session was designed to provide contributors with an overview of how governance tools and processes interact, while also inviting their reflections on transparency, accountability and the clarity of roles across CPAG, the Data Access Committee (DAC) and wider SDE operations.

Although the topics were technically complex, the meeting offered an important opportunity for contributors to understand how national frameworks are developing and to influence how these are communicated and designed. Their feedback highlighted where explanations were clear and supportive, where the pace or language created challenges, and where further clarity was needed to strengthen trust and shared decision-making. The perspectives and insights shared through CPAG meetings have been invaluable, and they will play a central role in guiding how we refine and enhance our approach and future work.

Public contributors were particularly attuned to questions of governance roles and decision-making authority during this CPAG session. Their reflections underscore the importance of clearly articulating how CPAG, the DAC and other oversight structures interact, and how public members can participate equitably in these processes. The sample of comments presented below demonstrate why transparent governance matters and why consistent communication is essential to supporting effective public involvement in technically complex AI and SDE governance work:

“We want reassurance that robust policies are in place – we don’t need the technical details, just transparency and accountability.” Public contributor, CPAG meeting on statistical disclosure checking

“How can we know that what we say has any results? Where do we see our impact?” Public contributor, CPAG meeting on Introduction to VISTA

“My assumption is that researchers are validated before they can even apply – that’s important for trust.” Public contributor, CPAG meeting on Introduction to VISTA

“Is there any way patients or the public can propose research projects for the SDE?” Public contributor, CPAG meeting on Introduction to VISTA

3.2.1. Key Learning Themes - Transparency and Clarity (PEDRI Standard: Transparency and Accountability)

Technical discussions involving SATRE, SACRO-ML, and AI governance created cognitive overload for some contributors. Frequent use of acronyms and specialist terminology limited engagement. The lessons to be learnt here is that supporting materials should include plain language agendas, visual explanations where feasible and acronym glossaries to assist with technical language familiarity.

3.2.2. Key Learning Themes - Role Clarity and Governance (PEDRI Standard: Governance and Accountability)

Public contributors expressed uncertainty about the respective roles of the CPAG and Data Access Committee (DAC), particularly regarding oversight of AI projects. A lesson learned was that clear governance maps are essential, outlining responsibilities, decision-making authority and escalation pathways to support transparency and effective collaboration.

3.2.3. Key Learning Themes - Inclusive Communication (PEDRI Standard: Inclusive Communication)

Technical discussions often progressed quickly, reducing opportunities for contributors to participate fully. Consequently, layered communication approaches are needed including high-level summaries with optional technical details, and active management of jargon.

3.2.4. Key Learning Themes - Ethics and Trust (PEDRI Standard: Ethics, Safety and Trust)

Public contributors raised concerns around AI model training and their potential for disclosing sensitive information data, and researcher access to raw data. These discussions reinforced the importance of clearly explaining existing safeguards.

3.3. SACRO - Statistical Disclosure Control (Joint CPAG with PANORAMA)

Statistical disclosure control (SDC) is a core safeguard within SDEs, ensuring that research outputs do not inadvertently reveal information about individuals, particularly when working with large, linked or highly granular datasets. For many public contributors, this was their first in-depth exposure to the mechanisms used to check outputs before they leave the environment, and the session offered an important opportunity to understand how privacy is actively protected in practice, not just in policy.

The CPAG meeting on SDC brought together contributors and SDE representatives to walk through the principles behind disclosure checking, the types of risks SDC is designed to prevent, and how different SDEs ensure consistency in decision-making. While the topic itself is inherently technical, the session was valued for its transparency and for opening a part of the researcher journey that is usually unseen by the public. It also surfaced important learning about the conditions required for meaningful public involvement in highly technical areas of governance.

Public contributors highlighted that although they recognised the importance of SDC, the complexity of the material, the pace of delivery, and the use of specialist terminology made it difficult to follow at points. Their reflections underscore the need for clearer explanations, visual materials, and structured pre-learning when introducing advanced governance mechanisms. These insights provide valuable guidance for strengthening future sessions and ensuring that discussions about technical safeguards remain accessible, inclusive and grounded in public understanding.

“The technical discussions were difficult to follow – separating technical and lay summaries would help.”

Public contributor, CPAG meeting on statistical disclosure checking

“We need clearer terminology. A glossary would be really useful.”

Public contributor, CPAG meeting on statistical disclosure checking

Public contributors valued the opportunity to discuss statistical disclosure control (SDC) but noted that the session assumed prior knowledge of technical concepts.

3.3.1. Key Learning Themes – Transparency (PEDRI Standard: Transparency)

Participants requested clearer explanations of how SDC fits within the wider SDE user journey. Strengthening this clarity would directly support the PEDRI standard in respect of transparency by ensuring people understand processes, decision points and the SDE user journey.

3.3.2. Key Learning Themes – Communication (PEDRI Standard: Inclusive Communication)

To ensure more inclusive communication, contributors suggested the use of visual diagrams (infographics), short videos and simple explanations to support understanding.

3.3.3. Key Learning Themes – Collaboration (PEDRI Standard: Governance and Partnership)

The session successfully brought together representatives from four SDEs, demonstrating the value of cross-programme collaboration. This collective engagement not only enabled richer sharing of experience and insight but also strengthened relationships across programmes. By working together in this way, we can align approaches more effectively, identify shared challenges earlier and co-develop solutions that benefit the wider community.

3.4. SACRO-ML CPAG Meeting

The SACRO-ML session introduced the governance framework used to assess AI projects within the Secure Data Environment to public contributors. It also introduced SACRO-ML, a tool designed to assess trained machine learning models for privacy risks before outputs leave the secure environment. Contributors appreciated the openness of the discussion and the opportunity to interrogate real-world examples, but they also emphasised where language, pace and specialist terminology created barriers to deeper understanding. Their reflections reinforce the importance of layered communication approaches, practical demonstrations, and ongoing training to support meaningful involvement in AI-related decision-making.

These insights provide valuable guidance for strengthening future CPAG agendas, refining public-facing materials on AI governance, and ensuring that public perspectives are central to the development of emerging national safeguards.

Public contributors emphasised the importance of transparency about evolving AI governance, early involvement in shaping safeguards and ongoing training to support confident participation. They also requested simplified visuals, broader real-world examples and access to dummy AI applications to strengthen DAC training. Together these insights highlight the need for clearer communication, practical learning tools, and meaningful engagement opportunities to ensure public contributors feel informed, empowered and equipped to participate effectively.

Public contributor insights around fairness, ethics & safety (AI & Output Checking) included:

“Is this more secure than what was used before? Have there been data breaches?” CPAG meeting on AI Risk assessment Tool

“For AI, how will you make sure models don’t accidentally ‘remember’ rare cases?” (Echoed in questions from multiple contributors.) CPAG meeting on AI Risk assessment Tool

“What happens when industry partners don’t want anyone to see their code? That’s their intellectual property.” Public contributor, CPAG meeting on Introduction to VISTA

These insights directly informed future governance design and training approaches.

3.5. SACRO-ML – AI Risk Assessment Toolkit CPAG Meeting

This meeting focused on the AI Risk Assessment Toolkit, with public contributors demonstrating strong engagement across complex governance topics such as privacy attacks, training/test separation and cumulative model risks. Their recommendations included simplifying technical language, improving documentation and clarifying governance processes. These insights directly informed enhancements to governance documentation, public-facing materials and future CPAG agendas.

Public contributors also highlighted several areas where adjustments would significantly improve accessibility and confidence during AI governance discussions, particularly the need to reduce reliance on jargon and specialist terminology. Taken together, these insights underscore the strategic importance of designing AI governance processes that are both technically robust and genuinely accessible, ensuring contributors can participate in their review with clarity, confidence and impact.

Contributors noted that the session introduced multiple unfamiliar terms in quick succession, making it difficult to stay engaged. As one contributor put it:

“It feels like learning a whole new language. When acronyms start rolling through, I switch off.”

They highlighted that substituting specialist language with plain English, where possible, would support clearer understanding:

“Use plainer English – for example, say ‘adds to’ instead of ‘augment’.”

This is especially important when introducing new national tools or frameworks and being cognisant of the need to manage the pace of technical discussion. The speed of explanation, combined with the density of the material discussed, created cognitive overload for some contributors. Slowing down the delivery, checking understanding at intervals, and layering information gradually were suggested as ways to support more inclusive discussion. It is also imperative that discussions are underpinned by clearer explanations of governance roles and decision pathways.

Contributors wanted to better understand how the CPAG fits into the AI risk assessment process, the relationship between CPAG, the DAC and technical governance teams and where decisions are made and who holds responsibility at each stage. Improving governance diagrams and providing step-by-step pathways would help make these relationships more transparent and understandable. Public contributors were clear that the use of more practical examples and demonstrations would greatly aid understanding.

Contributors found hypothetical or abstract explanations difficult to follow. Real-world examples, before-and-after demonstrations, or mock DAC cases were suggested as ways to make AI governance more tangible.

3.6. UK Trusted Research Environment (TRE) Community Conference (2025)

A recent national PPIE plenary session demonstrated the impact of meaningful collaboration between public contributors and professionals in high-level forums. A public contributor took an active role in the session, bringing visibility and credibility to public involvement at a national level and clearly showing how lived experience can meaningfully shape high-level discussions.

The session itself was a strong example of partnership working in practice. It blended lived experience, professional expertise and insights gathered from regional public engagement workshops, creating a balanced and compelling narrative that resonated with a wider audience. This collaborative approach not only enriched the quality of the discussion but also strengthened the national conversation on responsible data use.

The regional workshops which were the focus of the plenary session involved participants from across six East of England locations in partnership with 10 Healthwatch organisations. Participants ranged in age from 25 to 75 years, with representation including 12% Black participants and 10% LGBTQ+ participants.

The conference also highlighted the importance of ensuring that national conversations remain accessible and connected to real-world examples. For contributors, the impact of seeing concrete applications—such as an actual DAC case—created stronger motivation and clarity than abstract descriptions alone. This reinforces the need to design national engagement opportunities that help contributors visualise their role within the wider system. One public contributor reflected:

“It helps when things feel real, not abstract – like seeing an actual application in the DAC.”

Public contributor, CPAG meeting on Introduction to VISTA

At this event, public contributors were particularly keen to discuss data privacy, data flows and opt-out mechanisms and the processes that underpin responsible data use. Notably, the discussions reinforced the importance of recognising lived experience as equal to professional expertise. Subsequently, the discussions held at this event have influenced communication strategies and governance design within the SDE.

3.7. Feedback summary

Across all engagement activities, several consistent themes emerged regarding how public involvement can be strengthened within technically complex programmes.

Clarity and transparency are essential - Public contributors frequently highlighted that technical terminology, acronyms, and specialist language created barriers to participation. Sessions that included clear explanations, structured agendas, and accessible materials were significantly more successful in supporting meaningful engagement.

Public contributors can engage with complex governance topics when appropriately supported - Discussions on topics such as AI risk assessment, statistical disclosure control, and Secure Data Environment governance demonstrated that public contributors could engage deeply with complex issues when given sufficient context and learning support.

The design of engagement activities influences participation and confidence - Early Collaboration Café sessions revealed that unclear objectives and poorly structured discussions could unintentionally reinforce power imbalances between professionals and public contributors. Subsequent sessions that incorporated clearer facilitation and improved explanations were more inclusive and effective.

Public perspectives strengthen governance discussions - Public contributors raised important ethical questions regarding data privacy, AI model training, potential data disclosure risks, and transparency of safeguards. These contributions helped highlight areas where governance frameworks and communication materials could be improved.

Visible feedback loops are critical - Where feedback from public contributors was captured and shared with programme teams, it contributed to tangible improvements in future engagement activities. This demonstrates the value of structured reflection and continuous improvement.

The engagement activities described in this report demonstrate that public involvement can meaningfully inform national data infrastructure programmes, including discussions that are traditionally viewed as highly technical. Public contributors provided valuable insight into how governance processes, safeguards, and technical frameworks may be understood and perceived by wider communities.

These insights support improved communication, stronger transparency, and increased public confidence in the use of sensitive data for research.

While the programme demonstrates strong commitment to public involvement, several areas for improvement were identified:

- Improving the accessibility of technical discussions
- Providing clearer explanations of governance structures and decision-making processes
- Strengthening facilitation approaches to support equitable participation
- Ensuring public involvement is visibly reflected in technical outputs and publications

Across all activities, several consistent themes emerged.

1. Public trust is conditional

Trust depends on transparency, clear safeguards, and visible accountability. - *“We want reassurance that robust policies are in place – we don’t need the technical details, just transparency and accountability.”* Public contributor, CPAG meeting on statistical disclosure checking.

2. Lived experience strengthens governance

Public contributors identify blind spots and highlight real-world implications of technical decisions. - *“Different hospitals record the same thing differently – how can researchers compare anything?”* (This is prompted by the public contributor question and follow-on discussion.) Public contributor, CPAG meeting on Introduction to VISTA.

3. Communication is central to effective involvement

Without clear explanations, technical engagement risks excluding contributors. - *"...When acronyms start rolling through, I switch off."* Public contributor, CPAG meeting on Introduction to VISTA.

4. Public involvement strengthens legitimacy

Public representation within governance structures increases credibility and trust. *"If there are exceptions, they should go through the DAC with public members deciding."*

(Discussed around commercial use and proprietary code). Public contributor, CPAG meeting on Introduction to VISTA.

5. Iterative learning improves practice

Structured feedback mechanisms enable continuous improvement of involvement activities. - *"It helps when things feel real, not abstract – like seeing an actual application in the DAC."* (Public reflection during DAC debrief section.) Public contributor, CPAG meeting on Introduction to VISTA.

4. Conclusions

The activities described in this report demonstrate that public contributors can meaningfully engage with highly technical governance discussions when provided with accessible information, supportive learning environments and clear opportunities to influence decisions.

Embedding these principles across national data infrastructure programmes will strengthen transparency, accountability and public trust.

The VISTA team remains committed to ensuring that public involvement is treated with the same level of rigour and accountability as technical delivery.

The findings highlight that effective public involvement requires intentional design, ongoing support, and clear communication, particularly in programmes involving complex data governance and emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence.

By embedding these principles across future activities, the VISTA project, Eastern England SDE, and its partners can continue to strengthen public trust, transparency, and accountability in the development of national research data infrastructure.

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The project team would also like to express their sincere appreciation to all the public contributors who participated in this work for their valuable insights and constructive engagement throughout the project.

The authors have no conflict of interest to declare.

6. Glossary

CPAG – Core Public Advisory Group, the patient and public advisory group established for the Eastern England Secure Data Environment.

CUH – Cambridge University Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust

CUHP – Cambridge University Health Partners, academic health science centre with a mission to improve patient care by uniting the NHS, Industry and Academia

DAC – Data Access Committee, the group of governance, subject matter experts and members of the public who review and make access decisions for a given TRE.

DAR – Data Access Request, the form or document completed by a researcher to describe their research question and data needs so an access decision can be made for a given TRE.

DARE UK – Data and Analytics Research Environments UK, is a programme aimed towards establishing a safe and collaborative network of Trusted Research Environments.

EE-SDE – Eastern England Secure Data Environment, a platform for secure, controlled access to de-personalised patient data for research.

HIE – Health Innovation East, the innovation arm of the NHS in the East of England.

PPIE – Patient and Public Involvement and Engagement is the active partnership between researchers and the public to shape health research.

SACRO – Semi-Automated Checking of Research Outputs, is a semi-automated system of tools nested in the EE-SDE for checks on research outputs. It can enhance oversight and auditing for airlock managers.

SACRO-ML – Semi-Automated Checking of Research Outputs and ML, includes support for the managing of Statistical Disclosure Control of trained ML models engaged within the Secure Data Environment.

SATRE – Standardised Architecture for Trusted Research Environments, is a community-driven specification for the UK and beyond for building and operating Trusted Research Environments.

SDC – Statistical Disclosure Control, is a set of techniques used by airlock managers, or data custodians more broadly, to prevent the re-identification of individuals or entities in released data.

TRE – Trusted Research Environments, or otherwise Secure Data Environments are highly secure and controlled digital platforms allowing approved researchers access to sensitive, de-identified data for public interest research. These platforms house data and negate the need to move data around.

UKRI - UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) is a non-departmental public body sponsored by the Department for Science, Innovation and Technology (DSIT).

VISTA – VISTA (Viable Implementation of SATRE, SACRO and Tools for AI) is one of the DARE UK Early Adopter projects launched in January 2025. Led by Cambridge University Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust in partnership with Health Innovation East and Cambridge University Health Partners, VISTA is piloting TREvolution standards and AI capabilities within the Eastern England SDE

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